

ISic3129

I.Sicily inscription 3129

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Calacte

Place of origin (modern)

Caronia

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Caronia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333556

1. α Ἰ (ηοῦ) ς □ ω.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645470

PHI 333556

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 30.1124

Fiore, P. 1980. Alla ricerca di Solusapre. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 13: 31-38. At 37 fig.8-9

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